

SITE SPHINX I	DATE 7/VII/80	AREA T - RUMP LEGE	SQUARE	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top:	Bottom:
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter:	Width: TOP ≈ 26cm Bottom ≈ 4-5cm	Length: ≈ 1.00 m.	Depth: 70-75 cm	

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
1.	FINE THIN STONE FLAKES, FINE SAND (POWDER)	Light Grey - Buff	Fairly Packed	Matrix: Very Fine Powdery Chips concentrated	T	Lm ✓	Gp
					2 And small particles	Gr	Char ✓
					D	Do	
						Ba	
						Al ✓ 1 SMALL FRAG and Removal from Sifting	
Other *							
1b	Thin clay or Gypsum w. fine stone flakes	Light Grey Buff	Compact Fragile	Dry: Very Fine	T	Lm	Gp
					0	Gr	Char
					D	Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
Other							
2	FINE CLEAN SAND w. LIME-STONE FRAGS BOTTOM	Light Tan	Soft	Fine	T	Lm	Gp
					1 + small particles	Gr	Char Many Small Frags
					D	Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
Other	Few minute Grey mud spots *						
2a	SOFT FINE SAND	BUFF	LOOSE	SOFT	T	Lm	Gp
						Gr ✓ 1 small chip	Char ✓ **
					D	Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
Other	MORTAR - 1 large flat frag from sec. A						
3	TAN MORE CLAY-LIKE w. LARGE LIMESTONE CHIPS, MORTAR FRAGS CARBON FRAGS				T	Lm ✓	Gp
						Gr	Char ✓
					D	Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
Other	Mortar - 1 large flat frag from sec. A						

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/ C17 No./ 1, 2, 3	B&W: 14 Roll/ BW 14 No./ 1, 2, 3,
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DRAWN	Area Plan: 1:50 Stonework Plan: 1:20 Detail	Feature Plan:	Sections: 1:10
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: d1: SPACE BETWEEN "GEBEL" BOULDER AND CORE BODY.

* Small Cement frags coming up. Would like to think these crumbled off nearby edge of 1926 cement filling during excavation. as this edge very crumbly

* ①, At least at top part, likely mod. as frag cement comes up in second removal to section B. This is likely flaked, disintegrated core stone come down in last 50 years. Also another sherd, 1 carbon frag. straw fiber, hair embedded at top 2nd removal

+ ③ Taken together as ② in first removal to section A

NOTE: 2 (See section A) characterized by dry-separation lines as though laid down successive fine layers from moist surface(s) drying out. These surfaces break up into clumps during excavation (see photos C17-5 and BW14-5) 2a. contrasts as only loose fine sand

② 2nd Removal has some fine carbon and ceramic particles - but most carbon in level ③

** Large Carbon frags (less 1cm diam) come up immediately under, partially within ③ and show embedded in surface of ③.

OVER.

AT BOTTOM OF GEBEL BOULDER, ③ CONTAINS CONCENTRATED SHARP EDGED
LIMESTONE FRAGS - SMALL IN FILL AND LONG FLAT ONES STUCK INTO 2-4cm
space at bottom between Gebel Boulder and core